

METHODS OF DEVELOPING SIMULTANEOUS TRANSLATION SKILLS AMONG PUPILS IN SECONDARY EDUCATION

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Annotation: Methods for developing simultaneous translation skills in this article secondary school students Methods of developing simultaneous translation skills among pupils in secondary education and information on simultaneous reading and simultaneous speaking.

Key words: Simultaneous strategy, translation, teacher, components, Chernov, philosophy, speech, translation, translator, pronounced, phonetic, information.

The strategy of probabilistic forecasting in case of simultaneous translation is the attempt of the translator to foresee and work out lexical, grammatical, phonetic components of the speech of the speaker before they are pronounced, basing on already received and processed (i.e. translated) information. One of the methods of probabilistic forecasting is determination of any parts of speech in the text of the speaker. This method is especially productive when the main and semantic information of the statement is focused at the end of the sentence. For the first time the term "probabilistic forecasting" has been used by Russian scientist, the famous physiologist. According to Chernov's definition "probabilistic forecasting" is "A situation is a signal for preparation of body to react adequately to B situation. The wider range of the events which were equally often following A in the past (i.e. more uncertain is the forecast), the broader range of physiological systems will be mobilized in response to A signal. This prospective adaptation to actions in the forthcoming situation 198 relying on probabilistic structure of last experience can be called probabilistic forecasting". In Chernov's opinion mechanism of probabilistic forecasting is psycholinguistic mechanism providing simultaneous translation. This phenomenon is also widely investigated in the works of the academician Anokhin who claims that adaptive qualities which differ in the sequence and repeatability of events are inherent in all live organisms in the course of evolutionary development. We are convinced that process of implementation of probabilistic forecasting needs to be considered in the context of a real communicative situation as it differs in a combination of extra linguistic factors in the communication process. According to Chernov, it is possible to select set of elements or factors in a communicative situation of simultaneous translation which are identified in case of the response to the following questions: 1) who?

2) what ... with? 3) what subject? 4) before whom? 5) whom? 6) where? 7) when? 8) what purpose? 9) why? The translator needs to know the responses to these questions for successful implementation of the simultaneous translation. Probabilistic forecasting is multi-level, hierarchically connected mechanism each particle of which is in close connection with another. The probability of the correct forecasting increases in case of redundancy of the message and on the contrary, goes down in case of its insufficiency. It should be noted that, probabilistic forecasting is possible only if the text of the speaker consists of closely interconnected units. Sdobnikov and Petrova write that redundancy of language is shown at different levels. For example, at phonemic level: after one or two consonants there should be a vowel in Russian. At grammatical level: in the phrase "As the interconnected methods of any interconnected methodology..." the phenomenon of numerous sequences of words in gender, number and case, i.e. repetition of gender indication, number and case in a few words is observed. The conjunction "as" assumes appearance of the sentence, which will contain the consequence. The translator perceives the speech thanks to the necessary level of redundancy, providing thereby a possibility of probabilistic forecasting. It should be noted that availability of context increases redundancy that gives opportunity to the translator to perform probabilistic forecasting with accuracy that is more precise. "Being included to context, the Russian word form loses on average 1,6 units of the grammatical information containing in forms of the extra text word". Piotrovsky and other researchers established the redundancy reasons: 1) repeatability in speech flow of certain elements; 2) interdependence of linguistic components of the message. The fact that the sequence of components of the message (sounds, words, phrases, sentences and meanings) is formed on the basis of certain rules that make them interdependent, and leads to the fact that the source of the message is repeated. These conclusions are also basic provisions of theory of communication. Speaking about sub classification of probabilistic forecasting, it is worth mentioning that scholars differentiate two of them: a) "linguistic", or "syntactic" forecasting based on forecasting of a source of continuation of a discourse from knowledge of standard set of phrases and set expressions, such as undertake an obligation to... leave without a leg to stand on..., to functional words and unions which help to realize the meaning of statement; b) "extra-linguistic" forecasting based on external knowledge, extra-linguistic data which are possessed by the translator Types of simultaneous translation. In practice, there are three types (variants) of simultaneous translation: 1. Simultaneous translation of Yoda

(hearing). In this case, the interpreter through the headphones accepting the speaker's continuous speech and depending on how the information fall performs blocking translation. This is the most common and most complex case.

2. Synchronize according to the text with or without prior preparation translation. The simultaneous interpreter receives the text of the speaker's written speech in advance and translates according to the given materials. 3. Simultaneous reading of pre-translated text. Simultaneous interpreter speaker reads a preprepared text after the speech. Joiz in places where the speaker deviates from the original text during the speech makes corrections. Features of simultaneous translation. Simultaneous translation is one of the most important types of translation feature high efficiency, original text speech and translated speech the interval between is on average 3-4 seconds. At most 10 seconds. Therefore, the speaker is guaranteed to speak without interruption. there is no outside influence on the speaker's opinion and from the speech will not stop. This is so that the listeners fully understand the speech allows. This is why simultaneous translation is now a common practice in the world has become a method of translation. Today, 95% of the world's international meetings, simultaneous translation is used in conferences. However synchronous the translation has a great deal of scientific and professional character, and it is usually formal synchronous translation is extremely useful as it is used in international conferences high demands are placed. Simultaneous translation requirements. Simultaneous translation from the interpreter while he is speaking in the original language a short period of time based on thematic knowledge along with listening comprehension quickly predict, comprehend information in the original language it needs to be stored in memory and redirected. However different international conference, meetings with simultaneous interpreter "lightning thinking" will be able to do and have high speaking skills. IAIC (International Simultaneous Interpreters Association) decision, simultaneous interpreter can only translate 80% of the content of the participant-speaker is considered successful (90% -100% synchronous translation performed) cannot be increased). Most people are usually very fast talking, even when they are speaking, always the content of their speech text care about. On top of that, Ustak speaks in various local accents complicate. In these cases, the simultaneous interpreter has his own knowledge with all the power he has to move his treasure and experience will have to work. Deliberately speaking slowly about a simultaneous interpreter there aren't

many speakers who can care. This is the nature of the specialist places extremely high demands. The strategy of probabilistic forecasting in case of simultaneous translation is the attempt of the translator to foresee and work out lexical, grammatical, phonetic components of the speech of the speaker before they are pronounced, basing on already received and processed (i.e. translated) information. One of the methods of probabilistic forecasting is determination of any parts of speech in the text of the speaker. This method is especially productive when the main and semantic information of the statement is focused at the end of the sentence. For the first time the term "probabilistic forecasting" has been used by Russian scientist, the famous physiologist. According to Chernov's definition "probabilistic forecasting" is "A situation is a signal for preparation of body to react adequately to B situation. The wider range of the events which were equally often following A in the past (i.e. more uncertain is the forecast), the broader range of physiological systems will be mobilized in response to A signal. This prospective adaptation to actions in the forthcoming situation relying on probabilistic structure of last experience can be called probabilistic forecasting". In Chernov's opinion mechanism of probabilistic forecasting is psycholinguistic mechanism providing simultaneous translation. This phenomenon is also widely investigated in the works of the academician Anokhin who claims that adaptive qualities which differ in the sequence and repeatability of events are inherent in all live organisms the course of evolutionary development. We are convinced that process of implementation of probabilistic forecasting needs to be considered in the context of a real communicative situation as it differs in a combination of extra linguistic factors in the communication process. According to Chernov, it is possible to select set of elements or factors in a communicative situation of simultaneous translation which are identified in case of the response to the following questions: 1) who? 2) what ... with? 3) what subject? 4) before whom? 5) whom? 6) where? 7) when? 8) what purpose? 9) why? The translator needs to know the responses to these questions for successful implementation of the simultaneous translation. Probabilistic forecasting is multi-level, hierarchically connected mechanism each particle of which is in close connection with another. The probability of the correct forecasting increases in case of redundancy of the message and on the contrary, goes down in case of its insufficiency. It should be noted that, probabilistic forecasting is possible only if the text of the speaker consists of closely interconnected units. Sdobnikov and Petrova write that redundancy of language is shown at different levels. For example, at phonemic level: after one

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revealing the inner side of probabilistic forecasting as the bases of simultaneous translation.

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